

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

D 4.3

Report on international and national teacher trainings

Report on teacher training where teachers shared their experiences, lessons learned difficulties, ideas and possible suggestions related to the use of the bio economy teaching resources.

Document Description

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Executive Summary

This document aims to describe the results of the teacher trainings organized in the BLOOM project by offering a clear, straightforward, systematic overview.

The document is structured in two main parts. The first part includes general information about BLOOM teacher trainings with an overview of trainings organized by the pilot teachers per country, as well as the follow up activities on the implementations of BLOOM School Box by the trained teachers, organisation of three face-to-face meetings for BLOOM pilot teachers in Brussels, Belgium, and information about the dissemination activities of the BLOOM project by pilot teachers at the national and international level. Second part reflects on the organisation of the 'BLOOM Stories of Implementation' competition taking place between February and April 2020 as one of the actions pursued to ensure the BLOOM School Box reaches out to as many teachers as possible.

The main focus of this deliverable is on teacher trainings representing an important and strategic component for the dissemination and uptake of innovative STEM practices, and for the BLOOM project in particular, the uptake of bio economy by young citizens. Teachers are an indispensable medium for transmitting the applications of bioeconomy in education at local level. Through these trainings, the number of teachers who use bio economy in their lessons grew exponentially.

The BLOOM pilot teachers received continuous support from both European Schoolnet (EUN) and the project hubs and partners.

1. Introduction to the BLOOM teacher trainings

In BLOOM, 20 pilot teachers from ten countries are taking part in project activities (ten teacher coordinators and ten support teachers). These pilot teachers organized teacher trainings in their own countries, with the support from European Schoolnet (EUN), BLOOM Hubs (where applicable) and other project partners, to ensure the BLOOM School Box reaches out to as many teachers as possible:

The trainings aimed to achieve a **minimum of ten** participants trained per country. Furthermore, after each training, at least five of the trained participants were meant to implement one the BLOOM School Box lesson plans, with the support of the pilot teachers. In total, a minimum of ten BLOOM trainings were expected.

One of the core ideas behind the teacher trainings is BLOOM School Box as a way of introducing the concept of bioeconomy in classrooms. BLOOM School Box is the result of the work of pilot teachers who worked together for almost a year in an intensive creation-and-review process. As a result, The BLOOM School Box is available on the BLOOM repository (<https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/repository/>) and on a dedicated page on the BLOOM portal: <https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/>. By autumn 2019, the five learning scenarios developed by the BLOOM pilot teachers will be made available in German, Swedish, Spanish, Polish, Dutch and Finnish, in addition to English.

The purpose of the teacher trainings was twofold. Firstly, the trainings had the objective to raise awareness and enhance knowledge of bioeconomy among primary and secondary school STEM teachers. Secondly, the trainings aimed to empower trained teachers to use the BLOOM School Box in order to introduce the concepts and the perspectives of bioeconomy in their classrooms as a trigger to raise interest in science subjects and innovative practices.

This document also reflects on the ‘BLOOM Stories of Implementation’ Competition reaching out to teachers all over Europe who implemented BLOOM School Box learning scenarios in their classrooms or prepared an adaptation story based on those materials.

2. Teachers Coordinators Trainings

To ensure pilot schools' capacity in fulfilling their pre-defined tasks, EUN provided pilot teachers with three face-to-face trainings as described below. We are including several photos from the events in Annex 7.

2.1 First training during the 20th Science Projects Workshop

The 20th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab, organised by the Scientix and the BLOOM projects, took place in Brussels in March 2018, from Friday 02 Sunday 04. The event started with the networking dinner on Friday (19:30) and continued with the full day programme on Saturday (08:45-17:00) and half day programme on Sunday (08:45-12:30). In total 30 participants, including 22 teachers from 14 countries joined the event. After a common programme including an excellent introduction to Bioeconomy by Jelle van Leeuwen, Researcher Biorefinery from Wageningen Food & Biobased Research, participants were split depending on the project they are working on. The 10 BLOOM pilot teacher coordinators from Sweden, Italy, Austria, Greece, Croatia, Israel, Portugal, Poland, Spain and Belgium, have started working on the learning scenarios integrating bioeconomy in STEM classes which became public in 2019.

2.2 Second training during the 24th Science Projects Workshop

Second meeting, organized by BLOOM and Scientix, took place during the 24th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab in Brussels, Belgium, on 14 September (13:00-18:00) and 15 September (08:45-18:00) 2018. During this special workshop, 10 BLOOM teachers finalised their learning scenarios on how to integrate bioeconomy in Science, Technology, Engineering or Mathematics classes, which they then tested in classes, as well as learning about the next tasks, including training other teachers in their use and preparing materials for a MOOC launched in March 2019.

2.3 Third training during the 26th Science Project Workshop

The 26th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab, organised by BLOOM, took place in Brussels in January 2019, from Friday the 25th (13:00-17:30) to Saturday the 26th (08:45-17:30). In total, 20 participants from 10+ countries joined the event. The event represented the third meeting of the BLOOM Pilot teachers and provided an opportunity for these pedagogical experts in bioeconomy to finalise their work on the project. With the help of the four event facilitators, 16 teacher experts exchanged their experiences in testing the Bioeconomy Future Classroom Scenarios and contributed with their expertise to shaping the delivery of the BLOOM Massive Open Online Course, launched on the European Schoolnet academy on the 4th of March.

3. Teacher trainings organized by pilot teachers

From March to May 2019, BLOOM Pilot teachers organized 16 national and international trainings involving more than 200 participants. They documented the trainings activities in a report template (Annex 1) provided by EUN, together with the signed participants' list (template in Annex 2) and agenda of the event, if applicable.

Teachers were responsible for collecting the evaluation data via the training evaluation questionnaire in one of two ways. The first option was to print the questionnaire in their language, distribute it at the end of each training and collect the participants' responses. Once they had collected all questionnaires, they would need to input the translated responses of their participants into the digital, central English version of the evaluation questionnaire. The second option was to share directly with their participants the digital version of the questionnaire in case their participants felt comfortable to respond in English. The analysis of the data was done centrally by Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI), project coordinator and responsible for the project evaluation, according to the procedures stated in deliverable D5.2.

Section below outlines key information from the reports received per country.

3.1 Teacher training in Austria

One teacher training took place at the Faculty of Chemistry, University of Vienna, Austria, on the 15th of May 2019 with the title "How Can Bioeconomy Enrich Our Natural Science Lessons in the School?". The event engaged 14 participants, most of them being secondary school teachers in science, chemistry, biology, physics and mathematics. The event started with the introduction to bioeconomy and the presentation about the BLOOM project. Detailed explanations on using BLOOM School Box and experimenting using the scenario "Examining the thermal properties of bio-based building materials" were in focus. Organizers wrapped up the session by providing the participants the chance to reflect on the content by filling in the evaluation form. The teachers attending the event were not familiar with the topic and how to implement a bioeconomy-based learning scenario in their classroom prior the training. They appreciated the workshop in general, highlighting the importance of the experimental part.

3.2 Teacher trainings in Belgium

On the 20th of April 2019 one teacher training was conducted by the pilot teachers from Belgium with the title "BLOOM School Box Resources". The audience consisted of five pedagogical advisors and primary school teachers. Organizers aimed at familiarizing the participants with "Growing plastic and new life for plastic" School Box materials. Some of the hands-on experiments included activities such as identifying plastic, producing bioplastic and 3D printing. The reactions received were very positive and everyone expressed their motivation to apply the resources in their classrooms. Since the event was organized during

the Easter holidays, the main lesson learned was to plan the event during the school hours and to link the workshops to the bigger events, such as national science gatherings.

Another training took place on the 3rd of May 2019 involving 5 participants. This time, all the resources included in BLOOM School Box were presented, but again the special focus was on “Growing plastic and new life for plastic”. The trained teachers agreed that sustainability and environment can be embedded in all subject, except mathematics. The teachers mentioned that they will effectively communicate with each other in order to facilitate the collaboration efforts.

3.3 Teacher training in Spain

Pilot teachers in two different schools in Murcia, Spain organized two “All about bioeconomy” workshops on the 13th and 14th of May 2019 with the participation of 17 primary English and Science teachers, 9 in first, and 8 in the second one. They decided to use “How poop will change the world” School Box resources. Participating teachers were not very familiar with the concept of bioeconomy, but after the trainings most of them agreed that putting the lessons into practice with their pupils could be a great opportunity for the students to learn about biomass and bioeconomy. In the first workshops, teachers stressed the importance of adapting the content of the materials to second and third grade pupils. In the second workshop, fifth and sixth grade teachers stated that there is no reason for adaptation. The organizers mentioned in their report that they were very satisfied receiving positive feedback from the participants after the training and with the overall organisation of the event.

3.4 Teacher trainings in Greece

One international workshop took place on the 11th of April 2019 in Spata, Greece, involving 16 secondary school teachers from Greece, Italy and Spain aimed at “Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap” learning scenario. Teachers enjoyed the fruitful discussion about bioeconomy and BLOOM project in general. They became familiar with the equipment needed in order to implement the resources in the educational practices. The workshop was very well received by the participants.

One more national training was organized on the 15th of April 2019 (Spata, Greece) with 13 teachers involved. This event aimed on educating local teachers interested in agriculture. Therefore, they found the ideas of bioeconomy very useful.

3.5 Teacher training in Croatia

Teacher training in Croatia was conducted on the 6th of March 2019 in Vukovar, introducing bioeconomy and all the BLOOM School Box resources. The organizers used Mentimeter in order to evaluate the participants’ previous knowledge of bioeconomy. They presented biobased products and emphasised the importance of bioeconomy being present in

educational system. Participants (10) appreciated the content and expressed their interest in the topic as well as motivation to spread the idea among their colleagues.

3.6 Teacher training in Israel

Pilot teachers in Israel, while organizing their training session, focused on “Building a new environmental future” resources. One-and-a-half-hour workshop took place on the 29th of April 2019 at Tehnicon – Faculty of Education in Technology and Science in Haifa, Israel, involving 14 secondary school STEM teachers. They were engaged in an active discussion about the advantages and disadvantages of using the bioeconomy products and invited to prepare the individual and group argumentation. The practical part of the event consisted of carrying out the first lesson from “Building a new environmental future” resource.

3.7 Teacher trainings in Italy

One international training was organized on the 9th of April 2019 by the Italian pilot teachers in Vienna, Austria, during the EGU Committee on Education-Geosciences Information for Teachers (GIFT) workshop. The teachers were excited to learn about bioeconomy and how to use it in their classes. They conducted a small research on BLOOM projects’ website, School Box materials and BLOOM MOOC. They evaluated learning scenarios and made a distinction between the ones suitable for younger, and the ones for older pupils. The importance of being able to use the resources for free was highlighted. Some of the participants invited the organizers to conduct similar gatherings in their schools. The event engaged 19 teachers from all over Europe.

National edition of the workshop occurred in Sassari, Italy on the 12th of April 2019 as part of the largest science event in Sardinia, Italy. The event was attended by numerous students, STEM teachers, researchers and other stakeholders. During the 90’ workshop dedicated to “Growing plastic and new life for plastic” resources, 17 participants learned how to implement the materials in their own classrooms and agreed that the topic of bioeconomy is useful not only for teachers and students, but for the society in general.

3.8 Teacher training in Poland

One teacher training took Place in Warsaw, Poland on the 24th of April 2019, with the participation of 11 primary and secondary school teachers in science, chemistry, geography and informatics. The workshop was mainly aimed at “Examining the thermal prosperities of bio-based building materials”. Other than presenting bioeconomy, its science application and social/economical aspects, the session included experiment on investigating thermal insulation of bio-based and non-bio-based building materials with data logging. Participants discussed the results and provided very positive feedback regarding the workshop content.

3.9 Teacher trainings in Portugal

Two parallel workshops with the same content were conducted by pilot teachers in Portugal (in Alcanena and Entroncamento) on the 8th of May 2019 engaging 14 teachers in one school and 10 in another one. In the first part, the concepts of bioeconomy, green and circular economy were introduced. During the second, practical part, two different strategies were applied. In one of the schools the promoter was the teacher herself, while in the other one, students participated actively in the workshop in order to engage teachers. The organizers were very pleased with the outcome of the event and would not change anything in the future.

3.10 Teacher trainings in Sweden

On the 4th of April 2019, the first of two trainings took place in Kista, Sweden with 14 secondary STEM teachers participating. The pilot teacher managed to present all four BLOOM School Box learning scenarios. Teachers worked individually and in pairs while exploring the resources. Main lesson learned was to use the videos while presenting the project and the topic itself.

On the 22nd of May 2019 second event took place at the International English School in Uppsala, Sweden. Participants (7) were very interested in the topic and curious on how to implement BLOOM School Box learning scenarios in the next school years' lessons.

4. Learning Scenario implementations by trained teachers

Pilot teachers documented the implementations of the teachers they have trained via the teacher trainings. For this purpose, EUN created the template (Annex 3) with the aim of supporting the exchange of experience between the teachers and improving similar future processes. Trained teachers who implemented at least one of the BLOOM School Box lesson plans were provided with a certificate of achievement from EUN (Annex 4).

4.1 Austria

After the teacher training in Austria, five implementations of the BLOOM School Box learning scenarios took place, distributed between “Examining the thermal properties of bio-based building materials” (2), Growing plastic and new life for plastic (2) and Building a new environmental future (1). Participants perceived the lesson plans of the School Box as easy to use and very understandable. They were confident applying the lesson plans due to the fact that each lesson included in the learning scenario provides detailed description of the teaching steps. They implemented the lesson plans that fit best for their subjects: biology, chemistry, physics, mathematics (regression analysis) and computer science (3D printer). Parts of the materials were aimed towards students aged 12-14 (introduction to bioeconomy, plastic pollution, bioplastics, etc.), and the rest towards students aged 15-18.

4.2 Belgium

Following two teacher training events in Belgium, participants chose the following lesson plans for the implementation: “Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap lab” (1), “Growing plastic and new life for plastic” (4). The resources were slightly adapted by the teachers in order to be aligned with the national curriculum and primary school students. The implementation took place in technology and world orientation subjects. The teachers were positive about this experiment, stating that sharing experiences was the most motivating element for participating.

4.3 Spain

In Spain, all five participating teachers chose “How poop will change the world” resources as they found it the most suitable for primary school students. The lessons took the time previously estimated in the planning, two lesson of 60 minutes, 120 minutes in total for the entire development. The lesson was understandable for all participants. All the activities were well sequenced, and the materials provided were well designed in order to achieve the objectives planned. The materials were implemented with students whose age ranged between 10 and 13 years old as they were all teachers of Primary Education and the sessions were planned with this age target.

4.4 Greece

“Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap lab” lesson plan appeared to be the most popular resource in Greece, as it was implemented by four teachers, together with one implementation of “Growing plastic and new life for plastic” covering biology, chemistry and combined science. In general, teachers were enthusiastic about working with bioeconomy topics, which was unfamiliar to them. They found materials easy to use and concluded that scenarios are suitable for students aged 15 or more.

4.5 Croatia

In Croatia, ten teachers implemented one learning scenario: “How poop will change the world”. The time needed for the lesson was one hour and a half. Participants were sceptical towards the process as they did not have previous knowledge about bioeconomy, but still motivated to do a research on all materials included in the School Box, which gave them confidence to conduct the experiment. They evaluated the materials as very interesting, clear and understandable and they appreciated the support provided by the pilot teachers. Implemented lesson plans are linked with some of the Croatian curriculum parts and fit best for the students aged between 7 and 14.

4.6 Israel

Five teachers in Israel decided to implement “Building a new environmental future” learning scenario in biology, math, STEM and STEAM classes, involving students aged 12-17. Participants described the resources as clear, descriptive and instructive. However, some teachers mentioned challenges related to the language, and wish the videos from the lesson plan they used were translated into Hebrew, since not all the students understand English perfectly.

4.7 Italy

Trained teachers in Italy analysed all the learning scenarios from the BLOOM School Box but implemented some of the lessons related to plastic pollution due to the time constraints. Participants provided very positive feedback on the process, as resources were detailed and user-friendly. Some of the teachers mentioned that more hours on laboratory activities should be involved. They agreed to include the bioeconomy topics in the annual program for their classrooms.

4.8 Poland

Two teachers implemented Lesson Plan “How poop will change the world” in 8 classes. The implementation took approximately three hours for each class, one hour more than estimated.

Another participant implemented laboratory part of the “Examining the thermal properties of bio-based building materials” lesson plan. The implementation took two hours (as estimated in lesson plan). One teacher implemented “Building a new environmental future” materials. The implementation took three hours, but she did not conduct the whole scenario. The last implementation involved “Growing plastic and new life for plastic” and lasted for eight hours. No lack of content in the resources was reported. The teachers appreciated detailed description of the course and rich multimedia settings (videos, quizzes, presentations).

4.9 Sweden

Four implementations took place as follows: “Bloom your school with your biofuel and soap lab” (2), “Growing plastic and new life for plastic” (1), How poop will change the world (1). The process involved students aged 13-16. The teachers found it interesting to work on the lessons related to the new topic (bioeconomy). It was easy to adapt them as they were already tested by teachers. One of the participants suggested more videos to help students connect to the topic more. They also suggested that the lessons took longer than indicated in the actual plan. Although the lessons were done in science subjects, it was discussed they can be implemented in social studies as well as languages.

5. Summary of results

Table 1 provides a numerical overview of the events, participants and trained teachers per country.

Table 1: Number of the teacher trainings, participants and teachers who implemented BLOOM School Box Learning Scenarios

No of:	Aus tria	Belgium	Spain	Greece	Croatia	Israel	Italy	Poland	Portugal	Sweden	Total
Trainings	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	16
Participants	24	10	31	29	10	14	36	11	14	23	202
Trained teachers	5	5	5	5	10	5	5	5	-	4	49

6. Dissemination activities

Apart from the official teacher training activities, some of the pilot teachers presented BLOOM during various national and international events. For this purpose, EUN developed the template (Annex 5) in order to facilitate the reporting procedure. In total, information about 13 different dissemination activities including workshops, presentations, webinars, exhibitions and articles were documented.

7. 'BLOOM Stories of Implementation' Competition

7.1. Organisation of the competition

Organised as part of the STEM Discovery Campaign 2020, and supported by Scientix¹, the community for science education in Europe, the 'BLOOM Stories of Implementation' competition took place between 1 February and 30 April 2020. Participating teachers were asked to submit their "story of implementation" of bioeconomy concepts using BLOOM School Box learning scenarios in their classrooms by filling in a pre-defined template and submitting it in one of the four different categories of the competition:

- [1] Teaching bioeconomy in primary schools (individual work);
- [2] Teaching with bioeconomy in secondary schools' STEM classes (individual work);
- [3] Integrating STEM teaching with bioeconomy (teams of two STEM teachers of different subjects);
- [4] Integrating STEAM teaching with bioeconomy (teams of up to three teachers of different subjects, including at least one STEM teacher and at least one non-STEM teacher).

Due to the COVID-19 circumstances and many schools being closed, in March 2020, the organisers decided to adapt the competition to the new situation by encouraging teachers who haven't had the opportunity to implement their bioeconomy activities in their classroom to participate to the competition by writing a story of adaptation. Unlike stories of implementation, stories of adaptation didn't have to be implemented in the classroom. To write and submit their entries, teachers must have read the BLOOM School Box bioeconomy learning scenarios and write down how they would adapt them to fit online teaching.

Competitions' terms and conditions including all the necessary information for the participants can be found in Annex 6.

7.2. Judging process

As illustrated in Table 2: Submissions Summary, the competition had a total of 25 submissions. All stories were first revised by EUN, who selected the best 8 entries to go to the Jury review - these are considered finalists. Category 1 and 2 had three finalists each and one winner each. Category 3 and 4 had one finalist each and no winner.

¹ <http://www.scientix.eu/>

Table 2: 'BLOOM Stories of Implementation' Competition Submissions Summary

Summary	Category 1	Category 2	Category 3	Category 4	Total
Submissions	8	10	4	3	25
Finalists	3	3	1	1	8
Winners	1	1	0	0	2

The Jury Session took place online the 19th of May 2020, from 17:00 to 18:00 CET. All Jury members were present:

- Maarten Kootstra (Wageningen University and Research);
- Costantina Cossu (BLOOM expert teacher);
- Dr. Kiki Liadaki (BLOOM expert teacher),
- Seppe Hermans (BLOOM expert teacher);
- Stella Magid (BLOOM expert teacher).
- Agueda Gras-Velazquez (EUN) - coordinating the session
- Adriana Ressiore Campodonio (EUN) providing support.

The Jury members received the entries and had two weeks to review and grade them according to the grading criteria. EUN gathered the results from the jury members which were then discussed during the Jury sessions.

7.3 Results

BLOOM Stories Competition jury panel has decided to award the winners in the following categories:

- Teaching with bioeconomy in primary schools (individual work): “Bioeconomy for a sustainable future” by Semih-Essendemir (Turkey).
- Teaching bioeconomy in secondary schools’ STEM classes (individual work): “UNplasticize” by Honorata Pereira (Portugal).

The six finalists were:

- My kitchen without food waste (Marina Stanojlovic Mircic, Serbia)
- Sustainable development (Božica Borbaš, Croatia)
- Why bioenergy? (Elena Vladescu, Romania)
- Bioeconomics and Fruit (Natalia Grushko, Ukraine)
- Stay home and learn bioeconomy (Gjorgjina Dimova and Velika Markova, Republic of North Macedonia)
- Copernico in Bloom (Donata Federici Monesi and Patrizia Zambonelli, Italy)

Together with the finalists' entries, the winners' stories of adaptation and stories of implementation were made available in the BLOOM School Box.

The winners of the competition will also have the opportunity to participate in a podcast on Bioeconomy education.

The competition reached out to number of teachers from all around Europe, spreading the concept of bioeconomy and the use of its teaching resources.

8. Conclusion

With 16 teacher trainings organised at the national and international level across Europe, while only 10 was expected, we can conclude that BLOOM pilot teachers managed to organise and conduct teacher training successfully.

Most of the teachers stated in their reports that the participants of their trainings were not initially very familiar with the concept of bioeconomy so it was a good strategy from most of the teachers to split their workshops in two main parts: introduction of bioeconomy in general and presentation of the BLOOM School Box learning scenarios.

Teachers reported only minor organisational issues such as time constraints and the idea of linking trainings to larger events in the future.

Participants were eager to implement BLOOM School Box resources in their classroom and experienced no issues, while only adaptation of several components of the resources were needed, depending on the age of the students. They evaluated the BLOOM School Box materials understandable and easy to implement in almost all subjects.

They stated that they enjoyed the process as bioeconomy proved to be an important and useful topic not only for them and their students but for the society in general.

Raising awareness of bioeconomy among the wider public continued through the 'BLOOM Stories of Implementation' competition which once again inspired teachers to use the bioeconomy teaching resources included in the BLOOM School Box.

With dedicated BLOOM pilot teachers, teacher training events at the national and international level, BLOOM School Box repository and BLOOM 'Boosting Bioeconomy Knowledge in Schools' MOOC, bioeconomy had reached out to hundreds of teachers and students and will result with a strong impact on education shaping the values of the next generations.

9. List of Annexes:

1. Annex 1: BLOOM Teacher Training Reporting Form Template
2. Annex 2: BLOOM Teacher Training Signature List Template
3. Annex 3: BLOOM Teacher Training Implementation Reporting Template
4. Annex 4: BLOOM Scenario Implementation Certificate of Achievement Template
5. Annex 5: BLOOM Teacher Dissemination Report Template
6. Annex 6: BLOOM Stories of Implementation Competition Terms and Conditions
7. Annex 7: Photos from the Science Project Workshops in the Future Classroom Lab in Brussels, Belgium

BLOOM Teacher Training Reporting Form

General information about your teacher training	
Title of the training:	
Country:	
BLOOM teacher(s) organising the training:	
Date of the training:	
Venue/School of the training(s) you are reporting for:	
Duration of the training:	
Audience type <i>E.g.: primary school teachers, secondary school Maths teachers, etc.</i>	
Number of participants:	
Did your training focus on any particular School Box resources? Please specify.	
Overview of the programme	

Lesson learned

What did you learn from the experience? What were the reactions of your participants? What would you do differently in the future?

Pictures from the event

If consent was collected from participants

BLOOM Teacher Training - Signature list

<<Name of the event>>

<<Location>>, <<Date of the event>>

PARTICIPANTS

	Last Name	First Name	Country	Signature
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				

BLOOM teacher training – Implementation reporting template

The template was elaborated in order for you to document the implementations of the teachers you have trained via the teacher trainings.

This template aims at reflecting your experiences using the BLOOM school materials in your classes. Moreover, the template will support the exchange of experience between the teachers and to learn from each other. It aims at helping to improve similar future processes. Please take care to document your activities in a concise and clear manner.

General information about the training

Item	Description
Date of the training(s) you are reporting for	
Time of the training(s) you are reporting for	
Venue/School of the training(s) you are reporting for	

Basic information on testing the BLOOM school materials

Item	Description
Which subject(s) did your training participants choose to implement the BLOOM School Box?	
Which lesson plans of the School Box did the participants choose? Please name all.	<p><i>The five implementations took place as follows:</i></p> <p><i>Lesson plan [title 1] – 2 implementations</i></p> <p><i>Lesson plan [title 2] – 2 implementations</i></p> <p><i>Lesson plan [title 3] – 1 implementation</i></p>
What is the age and number of students that took part in the implementation of your training participants?	<p><i>Example: Teacher 1, [insert nr] students, ages Y-Z</i></p> <p><i>Teacher 2, [insert nr] students, ages A-B</i></p> <p>...</p>

Item	Description
Overall, how much time did it take each participant to implement the respective lesson plans? Was it more or less than what each lesson plan estimated?	<i>Example: Teacher 1 implemented Lesson Plan [insert title]. The implementation took approximately two more hours than what was estimated.</i>

Participants' perception of the BLOOM School Box

<p>How did the participants perceive applying the lesson plan of the School Box?</p> <p>Reflect and discuss about:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Was it easy to use? 2. Was the lesson plan understandable? 3. How confident did the participants feel applying the lesson plans of the school box? Why? 4. Is content missing from the implemented lesson plan? Why and which? 5. Is there content participants would take out of the implemented lesson plans? Why and which? 6. For which subjects do the implemented lesson plans fit best? Why? 7. For which ages are the implemented lesson plans most appropriate? Why? 	
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Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

Certificate of Achievement

This certificate is presented to

<<FirstName>> <<LastName>>
<<Country>>

in recognition of teaching bioeconomy with

The BLOOM School Box Learning Scenarios

Marc Durando

Executive Director, European Schoolnet

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BLOOM Teacher Dissemination Report

General information about your dissemination activity:	
Teachers' name:	
Date:	
Name of the event:	
City:	
Country:	
URL (if available):	
Type of dissemination activity (presentation, workshop, brochures):	
No. of brochures (if applicable):	
No. of participants (if applicable):	
Additional information about the activity/event:	

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

The BLOOM Stories

Competition

Terms and Conditions

Brussels, 1 February – 30 April 2020

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Introduction

All over Europe and beyond, teachers are looking for innovative ways of engaging their students with the big issues facing today's societies. In collaboration with the STEM Discovery Campaign 2020, the BLOOM project is inviting primary and secondary school teachers of all subjects to use bioeconomy as a way of engaging pupils in school subjects, and to share their stories!

The Competition is organised by BLOOM - Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation and part of the STEM Discovery Campaign 2020, supported by Scientix, the community for science education in Europe.

BLOOM - Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation (<https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/>) is an EU Coordination and Support Action implemented from 2017 to 2020. The project aims at bringing together partners from across Europe to debate, communicate, and engage the public in the potential of bioeconomy. An economy based on biomass promises to foster a circular economy and to enhance climate change mitigation, while reducing dependence on fossil fuels. The BLOOM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 773983.

The STEM Discovery Campaign is a yearly international initiative that invites projects, organisations and schools across Europe and around the world, to celebrate careers and studies in the fields of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). The STEM Discovery Campaign is supported by **Scientix** (<http://scientix.eu>), the Community for Science Education in Europe. Scientix promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals. Scientix has been running since 2010 organizing teacher-training activities, dissemination conferences and events, and supporting the exchange of knowledge and experiences in STEM Education via its portal, publications and events. Scientix is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and coordinated by European Schoolnet.

Categories

Categories

Participating teachers are asked to submit their “story of implementation” or “story of adaptation” of bioeconomy concepts using [BLOOM School Box](#) learning scenarios in their classrooms by filling in a pre-defined template and submitting it in one of the four different categories of the competition:

- [1] Teaching bioeconomy in primary schools (individual work);
- [2] Teaching with bioeconomy in secondary schools’ STEM classes (individual work);
- [3] Integrating STEM teaching with bioeconomy (teams of two STEM teachers of different subjects);
- [4] Integrating STEAM teaching with bioeconomy (teams of up to three teachers of different subjects, including at least one STEM teacher and at least one non-STEM teacher).

Submissions to the competition will be made via the STEM Discovery Week submission form, which will be made available on the BLOOM portal since 1 February 2020.

Each submission to the competition will consist of one submission form, filled in either by one individual or by teams of two or up to three participants, according to the requirements of each category.

The entry requirements for each competition category are the following:

[1] Entry requirements for the category: Teaching with bioeconomy in primary schools (individual work)

Participants in this category must be primary school teachers who wrote a story of implementation or a story of adaptation of at least one of the BLOOM School Box resources. The story submitted must be the work of one individual primary school teacher to be eligible for participation in this category.

[2] Entry requirements for the category: Teaching with bioeconomy in secondary schools’ STEM classes (individual work)

Participants in this category must be secondary school teachers of one or more STEM subjects who wrote a story of implementation or a story of adaptation of at least one of the BLOOM School Box resources. They should teach Science, Technology, Engineering or Mathematics (STEM). The story submitted must be the work of one individual secondary school STEM teacher to be eligible for participation in this category.

[3] Entry requirements for the category: Integrating STEM teaching with bioeconomy (collaborative teaching)

Participants in this category will be secondary school STEM teachers, applying in teams of two, who have collaborated in the implementation, or collaboratively written a story of adaptation of at least one of the BLOOM School Box resources. They should teach Science, Technology, Engineering or Mathematics (STEM).

The story submitted must be the work of two secondary school STEM teachers of different subjects to be eligible for participation in this category.

[4] **Entry requirements for the category:** Integrating STEAM teaching with bioeconomy (collaborative teaching)

Participants in this category will be secondary school STEM teachers and teachers of other subjects, applying in teams of up to three, including at least one STEM teacher and at least one non-STEM teacher. The teams have collaborated in the implementation or in the conception of the story of adaptation of at least one of the BLOOM School Box resources.

The story submitted must be the work of up to three secondary school teachers as detailed above to be eligible for participation in this category.

Eligibility

The Competition is open to all **primary and secondary school teachers** from European Union countries and [Horizon 2020 associated countries](#) who implemented a BLOOM School Box learning scenario in their classrooms or virtually, and/or who wrote a story of adaptation on how they would implement a BLOOM School Box learning scenario in their classroom. Only entries in English, which follow the official competition template, and which are submitted during the official submission period (as outlined in section 3) will be eligible for this competition.

Participation in the competition is subject to the rules and terms and conditions outlined in this document, and to the BLOOM decisions, which are final and binding in all respects and not subject to appeal. Due to the high number of nominations received, European Schoolnet will not offer individual feedback or enter into discussions regarding the awarded “stories of implementation or adaptation”.

Submission

How to submit

During the submission period of the competition indicated below (section 3.2), teachers can submit their entries by going through the steps below:

Step 1: Prepare their bioeconomy “stories of implementation or adaptation” according to the competition template that can be found in the Competition Toolkit.

Step 2: Fill in the online competition submission form available on the competition page in the [BLOOM portal](#).

Important note: All information must be submitted by the 30 April 2020 at 23:59 Central European Time (CET) in order to be eligible for the competition. All content included in the submission form (including links with supporting material) must be available for view and download until at least 30 days after the end of the submission period (see below in the Submission period section). The email address(es) provided in the submission form must be valid.

Submission period

Submissions for all four competition categories will be accepted between **1 February** and **30 April 2020** at 23:59 Central European Time (CET). Submissions received outside the submission period will not be eligible for participation.

The submitted content

The submitted content for the competition shall be an **original creation** by **one (for submission categories [1] and [2]), two (for submission category [3]) or up to three (for submission category [4]) participating teachers** and consist of a “story of implementation” or “story of adaptation” of one of the BLOOM School Box learning scenarios in the classroom.

The submitted work should:

- Follow the official submission template provided on the competition webpage
- Be one standalone document, no attachments will be considered that are not part of the submitted “Story of Implementation” or “Story of adaptation” template. Be completely original and not contain any third party’s work.

By participating in the competition, participants agree to present their submitted content under a Creative Commons License of Attribution ShareAlike CC BY-SA.

Judging process

The entries will be considered at two stages:

- 1) A first selection of up to 20 finalist submissions (5 for each category) will be carried out by European Schoolnet.
- 2) The winner(s) of each category will be selected from the finalists identified in the previous stage, by an international panel of judges including bioeconomy experts and education specialists from the BLOOM project partner organisations.

Scoring criteria

The following criteria will be applied to evaluate the submissions to the BLOOM Competition:

- **Alignment with BLOOM** – the extent to which the entry built on the chosen School Box resource
- **Creativity and innovation** – how the resource was incorporated in the classroom or online
- **Impact and evidence** – clear presentation of learning outcomes and supporting evidence

- **Clarity of ideas and conclusions** - explaining in a clear way, demonstrating a good understanding of the theme and conveying convincing implementation methods, solutions and messages
- **Presentation of entries:** style, layout, design and good use of technology will be considered
- **Sharing good practice** – clear advice points and learning tips to help other teachers, to take a similar approach in the future. **For participants in categories 3 and 4** (collaborative teaching) – clear presentation of aspects related to collaborative work and of the outcomes of the collaboration.

Awards

1. The winners of each category will be invited to a teacher training workshop in Brussels, with travel, accommodation and meals covered. European Schoolnet might adapt the prizes should the event in Brussels not be possible.
2. The 20 finalist “stories of implementation or adaptation” will be published online on [the School Network page](#) of the BLOOM project.
3. All participants whose submissions comply with the Terms and Conditions of participation outlined in this document will receive a certificate of participation where the name of a registered participant and country will be specified. One single certificate of participation per person will be issued, regardless if he/she participated in one or more categories, with one or more entries, and if the name repeats several times. The certificates will be sent to the email addresses specified in the competition submission forms. The winners and remaining 20 finalists will get a different certificate specifying their achievements.

Notification of winners

Potential winners will be contacted by BLOOM representatives via the contact information provided in the submission form.

In all cases, in order to remain eligible to be awarded with a prize, a winner must respond to the winner notification contact (i.e., via email or comment, as the case may be) and commence the prize claim procedure within 72 hours of transmission/posting of contact. In the event of noncompliance with these requirements, if a potential winner cannot be reached for any reason (including failure to receive or respond to contact for any reason) or if a potential winner is determined to be ineligible or otherwise in violation of these terms and conditions, he/she shall be disqualified and forfeit the prize. In case of prize forfeiture, alternate winner(s) will be selected, taking into consideration the scoring criteria outlined in section 4.1.

Releases: By accepting a prize, the winner allows BLOOM to use his/her name and winning submission to be disseminated as the result of the competition. In case of any problems during the running of the competition, BLOOM keeps the right to modify any of the previous conditions.

Entry Restrictions

There is a limit of **three** submissions for the competition by the same participant.

- DO NOT submit the same “story of implementation” or “story of adaptation” more than once.
- DO NOT use the same resource(s) to create several ““story of implementation” or “story of adaptation”.
- A given e-mail account may only be used by one person to participate in the competition. Any dispute as to the identity any of the prize winners will be resolved by BLOOM in its sole discretion.

Content Restrictions

Submitted content must comply with the following criteria:

- (a) Content must be original and neither copied, as a whole or partly, nor rephrased from any other source
- (b) Content must be truthful
- (c) Content must not violate the rights of any third party
- (d) Content must not be inappropriate or unfit for publication (e.g. include nudity, obscenity or hate speech)
- (e) If your submission shows faces, please be aware that you **MUST** be in possession of the signed authorisation of all persons appearing in the videos and/or pictures. In addition, for underage students you must get their legal guardians’ agreement before using their images. Authorisation form templates are available in the Competition Toolkit available on the competition page for: young people under 18 years old (BLOOM-Comp-Permission-form-students.pdf) and for adults (BLOOM-Comp-Permission-form-adults.pdf). Please be aware that EUN Partnership aisbl will request signed authorizations for all persons appearing on your video/image submitted to the competition if the submission is selected to be published on the portal (short-listed and winners).

License of the content

By participating in the competition, participants accept that the submitted content follows a Creative Commons License of Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0). Details of this license can be found here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

All participants are made aware that in order to use any copyrighted material – images, music, video – they need to be in possession of the permission of the author in written form. EUN Partnership aisbl reserves the right to request clarification on the copyrights of the materials

submitted to the competition. Participants are required to read carefully the full details in sections Content restrictions and Legal aspects.

Legal aspects

All participants must comply with European and national laws including, but not limited to, copyright laws, legislation prohibiting the publication of any defamatory, discriminatory or other illegal content and any other similar laws.

The “BLOOM Stories” competition (“the Competition”) is organized by EUN Partnership aisbl (“Organizer”).

By registering and uploading content, contestants declare that the content submitted is their original work and creation. The Organizer does not assume any responsibility for disputes between persons claiming copyrights of content. By registering and uploading content, each contestant declares that the content does not infringe any third party rights and that they have obtained all necessary rights and licenses from third parties for the use of any materials. Contestants may not use any music that is not in the public domain or for which they have not acquired the necessary rights and licenses. The contestants will be fully responsible to the Organizer for any breach of the conditions contained in this disclaimer and, in particular, will hold the organizer harmless from any actions brought by third parties.

The Organizer reserves the right to exclude proposals submitted for the Competition if it comes to their knowledge that there are copyright infringements or the content contains defamatory, discriminatory or other illegal material or does not comply with national legislation.

By registering and uploading content, the contestants agree that the Organizer shall have the right to make the content freely available for non-commercial educational purposes on the web, CD-ROM or in any other media format for a period of three years starting from the date of the close of entries for the Competition.

By registering and uploading content the contestants declare that all identifiable individuals in their entry consented to the use of their image/performance, the submission of the content in this competition, and the use of the content by the Organizer for non-commercial educational and promotional purposes in all media formats, including the web, for a period of three years from the date of the close of entries for the Competition. Contestants declare that the individuals who have provided content for their submission will sign all necessary documents granting the Organizer, if required by it, the rights free of charge to use the content as indicated above.

For promotional purposes, the winners at national level may be requested to make available a presentation for the Organizer of their entry in a publicly available format, e.g. a trailer, teaser, screenshot etc. By submitting their content, contestants declare their agreement that the Organizer may freely use this presentation in all media formats in its promotional activities of the award, in case it is requested. The Organizer shall have complete discretion regarding how they want to claim and exercise these rights.

Privacy policy

The Organiser will process any personal data in accordance with the “Data Protection and Processing” provisions outlined in the Competition submission form.

If selected as one of the 20 finalists of the “BLOOM Stories” competition, the work of participants will be shared with the members of the Competition Jury, as part of the judging process. To ensure impartiality during the judging process, all works will be submitted to the jury under a pseudonym. No personal information will be shared outside EUN Partnership aisbl during this process.

Contacts

If you have any questions regarding the STEM Discovery Campaign, please contact Eleni Myrtsioti (eleni.myrtsioti@eun.org)

If you any questions about the “BLOOM Stories”, participants may contact Bori Pocze, at: borbala.pocze@eun.org

All participants have the right to contact the Organizer at any time and ask for corrections to any personal data held on them or ask for it to be deleted:

By e-mail: privacy@eun.org

By Mail:

Data Controller/Internal Auditor
EUN Partnership aisbl
Rue de Trèves 61
B-1040 Brussels
Data controller/Internal Auditor

If participants feel that the Organiser has not dealt correctly with any personal data (see section above) or wish to make an official complaint, they will be given the contact details of the Belgian Data Protection Authorities:

Belgian Data Protection Authority

Rue de la Presse, 35,
1000 Bruxelles
+32 (0)2 274 48 00
+32 (0)2 274 48 35 contact@apd-gba.be

Science Project Workshops in the Future Classroom Lab in Brussels, Belgium

